

The refined indefinite neutrosophic integral

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Abstract: This work presented the refined neutrosophic indefinite integral, where the substitution method for calculating integrals in the refined neutrosophic field that contain two part of indeterminacy (I_1, I_2) was presented. We also proved a theorem through which we were able to find most of the integrals for the refined neutrosophic functions.

Keywords: refined neutrosophic indefinite integral; substitution; indeterminacy.

1. Introduction and Preliminaries

To describe a mathematical model of uncertainty, vagueness, ambiguity, imprecision, undefined, unknown, incompleteness, inconsistency, redundancy, and contradiction, Smarandache suggested the neutrosophic Logic as an alternative to the current logics. Smarandache made refined neutrosophic numbers available in the following form: $(a, b_1I_1, b_2I_2, \dots, b_nI_n)$ where $a, b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n \in R$ or C [1]

Agboola introduced the concept of refined neutrosophic algebraic structures [2]. Also, the refined neutrosophic rings I was studied in paper [3], where it assumed that I splits into two indeterminacies I_1 [contradiction (true (T) and false (F))] and I_2 [ignorance (true (T) or false (F))]. It then follows logically that: [3]

$$I_1I_1 = I_1^2 = I_1 \quad (1)$$

$$I_2I_2 = I_2^2 = I_2 \quad (2)$$

$$I_1I_2 = I_2I_1 = I_1 \quad (3)$$

In addition, there are many papers presenting studies on refined neutrosophic numbers [4-5-6-7-8]. Smarandache discussed neutrosophic indefinite integral (Refined Indeterminacy) [11]

Let $g: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{I_1\} \cup \{I_2\} \cup \{I_3\}$, where I_1, I_2 , and I_3 are types of sub indeterminacies,

$$g(x) = 7x - 2I_1 + x^2I_2 + 4x^3I_3$$

then:

$$F(x) = \int [7x - 2I_1 + x^2I_2 + 4x^3I_3] dx$$

$$= \frac{7x^2}{2} - 2xI_1 + \frac{x^3}{3}I_2 + x^4I_3 + a + bI_1 + cI_2 + dI_3$$

where a and b are real constants.

Alhasan also presented several papers on calculus, in which he discussed neutrosophic definite and indefinite integrals. He also presented the most important applications of definite integrals in neutrosophic logic [9-10].

Integration is important in human life, and one of its most important applications is the calculation of area, size and arc length. In our reality we find things that cannot be precisely defined, and that contain an indeterminacy part. This is the reason for studying neutrosophic integration and methods of its integration in this paper.

This paper dealt with several topics, in the first part of which introduction and preliminaries were presented, and in the main discussion part the refined neutrosophic indefinite integral that contain two part of indeterminacy (I_1, I_2). In the last part, a conclusion to the paper is given.

2. Main Discussion

The refined neutrosophic indefinite integral

Definition 1

Let $f: R(I_1, I_2) \rightarrow R(I_1, I_2)$, to evaluate $\int f(x, I_1, I_2)dx$

put: $x = g(u) \Rightarrow dx = g'(u)du$

by substitution, we get:

$$\int f(x, I_1, I_2)dx = \int f(u)g'(u)du$$

then we can directly integral it.

Theorem 1

If $\int f(x, I_1, I_2)dx = \varphi(x, I_1, I_2)$, then:

$$\int f((\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2) dx = \left(\frac{1}{\dot{a}} + \left[\frac{-\dot{a}\dot{b}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})(\dot{a} + \dot{b} + \dot{c})} \right] I_1 - \left[\frac{\dot{c}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})} \right] I_2 \right) \varphi((\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2) + C$$

where C is an indeterminate real constant (i.e. constant of the form $a + bI_1 + cI_2$, where a, b, c are real numbers, while $I_1, I_2 =$ indeterminacy) and $\dot{a}_2 \neq 0$, $\dot{a}_2 \neq -\dot{c}_2$ and $\dot{a}_2 \neq -\dot{b}_2 - \dot{c}_2$

Proof:

put: $(\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2 = u \Rightarrow (\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)dx = du$

$$\Rightarrow dx = \frac{1}{\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2} du$$

$$\Rightarrow dx = \left(\frac{1}{\dot{a}} + \left[\frac{-\dot{a}\dot{b}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})(\dot{a} + \dot{b} + \dot{c})} \right] I_1 - \left[\frac{\dot{c}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})} \right] I_2 \right) du$$

$$\int f((\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2) dx = \int f(u) \left(\frac{1}{\dot{a}} + \left[\frac{-\dot{a}\dot{b}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})(\dot{a} + \dot{b} + \dot{c})} \right] I_1 - \left[\frac{\dot{c}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})} \right] I_2 \right) du$$

$$= \left(\frac{1}{\dot{a}} + \left[\frac{-\dot{a}\dot{b}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})(\dot{a} + \dot{b} + \dot{c})} \right] I_1 - \left[\frac{\dot{c}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})} \right] I_2 \right) \varphi(u) + C$$

back to the variable x , we get:

$$\int f((\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2) dx \\ = \left(\frac{1}{\dot{a}} + \left[\frac{-\dot{a}\dot{b}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})(\dot{a} + \dot{b} + \dot{c})} \right] I_1 - \left[\frac{\dot{c}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})} \right] I_2 \right) \varphi((\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2) + C$$

Using the previous theorem, we get on:

$$1) \int ((\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2)^n dx$$

$$= \left(\frac{1}{\dot{a}} + \left[\frac{-\dot{a}\dot{b}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})(\dot{a} + \dot{b} + \dot{c})} \right] I_1 - \left[\frac{\dot{c}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})} \right] I_2 \right) \frac{((\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2)^{n+1}}{n+1} + C$$

$$2) \int \frac{1}{(\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2} dx$$

$$= \left(\frac{1}{\dot{a}} + \left[\frac{-\dot{a}\dot{b}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})(\dot{a} + \dot{b} + \dot{c})} \right] I_1 - \left[\frac{\dot{c}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})} \right] I_2 \right) \ln|(\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2| + C$$

$$3) \int e^{(\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2} dx$$

$$= \left(\frac{1}{\dot{a}} + \left[\frac{-\dot{a}\dot{b}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})(\dot{a} + \dot{b} + \dot{c})} \right] I_1 - \left[\frac{\dot{c}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})} \right] I_2 \right) e^{(\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2} + C$$

$$4) \int \frac{1}{\sqrt{(\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2}} dx$$

$$= 2 \left(\frac{1}{\dot{a}} + \left[\frac{-\dot{a}\dot{b}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})(\dot{a} + \dot{b} + \dot{c})} \right] I_1 - \left[\frac{\dot{c}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})} \right] I_2 \right) \sqrt{(\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2} + C$$

$$5) \int \cos((\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2) dx$$

$$= \left(\frac{1}{\dot{a}} + \left[\frac{-\dot{a}\dot{b}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})(\dot{a} + \dot{b} + \dot{c})} \right] I_1 - \left[\frac{\dot{c}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})} \right] I_2 \right) \sin((\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2) + C$$

$$6) \int \sin((\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2) dx$$

$$= - \left(\frac{1}{\dot{a}} + \left[\frac{-\dot{a}\dot{b}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})(\dot{a} + \dot{b} + \dot{c})} \right] I_1 - \left[\frac{\dot{c}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})} \right] I_2 \right) \cos((\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2) + C$$

- 7)
$$\int \sec^2 \left((\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2 \right) dx$$

$$= \left(\frac{1}{\dot{a}} - \frac{b}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + b)} I \right) \tan \left((\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2 \right) + C$$
- 8)
$$\int \csc^2 \left((\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2 \right) dx$$

$$= - \left(\frac{1}{\dot{a}} + \left[\frac{-\dot{a}\dot{b}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})(\dot{a} + \dot{b} + \dot{c})} \right] I_1 - \left[\frac{\dot{c}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})} \right] I_2 \right) \cot \left((\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2 \right) + C$$
- 9)
$$\int \sec \left((\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2 \right) \tan \left((\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2 \right) dx$$

$$= \left(\frac{1}{\dot{a}} + \left[\frac{-\dot{a}\dot{b}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})(\dot{a} + \dot{b} + \dot{c})} \right] I_1 - \left[\frac{\dot{c}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})} \right] I_2 \right) \sec \left((\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2 \right) + C$$
- 10)
$$\int \csc \left((\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2 \right) \cot \left((\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2 \right) dx$$

$$= - \left(\frac{1}{\dot{a}} + \left[\frac{-\dot{a}\dot{b}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})(\dot{a} + \dot{b} + \dot{c})} \right] I_1 - \left[\frac{\dot{c}}{\dot{a}(\dot{a} + \dot{c})} \right] I_2 \right) \csc \left((\dot{a} + \dot{b}I_1 + \dot{c}I_2)x + r + sI_1 + tI_2 \right) + C$$

Example 1

- 1)
$$\int ((2 - 4I_1 + 3I_2)x + 7)^8 dx = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \left[\frac{8}{(2)(5)(1)} \right] I_1 - \left[\frac{3}{(2)(5)} \right] I_2 \right) \frac{((2 - 4I_1 + 3I_2)x + 7)^9}{9} + C$$

$$= \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{4}{5} I_1 - \frac{3}{10} I_2 \right) \frac{((2 - 4I_1 + 3I_2)x + 7)^9}{9} + C$$
- 2)
$$\int \frac{1}{(7 - 5I_1 + 6I_2)x + 2I_1 + I_2} dx$$

$$= \left(\frac{1}{7} + \left[\frac{35}{(7)(13)(8)} \right] I_1 - \left[\frac{6}{(7)(13)} \right] I_2 \right) \ln |(7 - 5I_1 + 6I_2)x + 2I_1 + I_2| + C$$

$$= \left(\frac{1}{7} + \frac{5}{104} I_1 - \frac{6}{91} I_2 \right) \ln |(7 - 5I_1 + 6I_2)x + 2I_1 + I_2| + C$$
- 3)
$$\int e^{(1+I_2)x-6I_2} dx = \left(1 + \left[\frac{0}{(1)(2)(2)} \right] I_1 - \left[\frac{1}{(1)(2)} \right] I_2 \right) e^{(1+I_2)x-6I_2} + C$$

$$= \left(1 - \frac{1}{2} I_2 \right) e^{(1+I_2)x-6I_2} + C$$
- 4)
$$\int \cos((3 + 3I_1 + 9I_2)x + 7I_1) dx$$

$$= \left(\frac{1}{3} + \left[\frac{-9}{(3)(12)(15)} \right] I_1 - \left[\frac{9}{(3)(12)} \right] I_2 \right) \sin((3 + 3I_1 + 9I_2)x + 7I_1) + C$$

$$= \left(\frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{6} I_1 - \frac{1}{4} I_2 \right) \sin((3 + 3I_1 + 9I_2)x + 7I_1) + C$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5) \int \sec^2((-4 + 3I_1 + 8I_2)x - 2I_2) dx \\
&= \left(\frac{-1}{4} + \left[\frac{12}{(-4)(4)(7)}\right]I_1 - \left[\frac{8}{(-4)(4)}\right]I_2\right) \tan((-4 + 3I_1 + 8I_2)x - 2I_2) + C \\
&= \left(\frac{-1}{4} - \frac{3}{28}I_1 + \frac{1}{2}I_2\right) \tan((-4 + 3I_1 + 8I_2)x - 2I_2) + C
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6) \int \csc((1 - 3I_1 + I_2)x) \cot((1 - 3I_1 + I_2)x) dx \\
&= -\left(1 + \left[\frac{3}{(1)(2)(-1)}\right]I_1 - \left[\frac{1}{(1)(2)}\right]I_2\right) \csc((1 - 3I_1 + I_2)x) + C \\
&= -\left(1 - \frac{3}{2}I_1 - \frac{1}{2}I_2\right) \csc((1 - 3I_1 + I_2)x) + C \\
&= \left(-1 + \frac{3}{2}I_1 + \frac{1}{2}I_2\right) \csc((1 - 3I_1 + I_2)x) + C
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7) \int \frac{1}{\sqrt{(10 - I_1 + 8I_2)x + 9 - 4I_1}} dx \\
&= 2\left(\frac{1}{10} + \left[\frac{10}{(10)(18)(17)}\right]I_1 - \left[\frac{8}{(10)(18)}\right]I_2\right) \sqrt{(10 - I_1 + 8I_2)x + 9 - 4I_1} + C \\
&= 2\left(\frac{1}{10} + \frac{1}{306}I_1 - \frac{2}{45}I_2\right) \sqrt{(10 - I_1 + 8I_2)x + 9 - 4I_1} + C \\
&= \left(\frac{1}{5} + \frac{2}{306}I_1 - \frac{4}{45}I_2\right) \sqrt{(10 - I_1 + 8I_2)x + 9 - 4I_1} + C
\end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2

Let $f: R(I_1, I_2) \rightarrow R(I_1, I_2)$, then:

$$\int \frac{\dot{f}(x, I_1, I_2)}{f(x, I_1, I_2)} dx = \ln|f(x, I_1, I_2)| + C$$

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{put: } f(x, I_1, I_2) = u &\Rightarrow \dot{f}(x, I_1, I_2) dx = du \\
&\Rightarrow dx = \frac{1}{\dot{f}(x, I_1, I_2)} du \\
&\Rightarrow dx = \frac{1}{\dot{u}} du
\end{aligned}$$

$$\int \frac{\dot{f}(x, I_1, I_2)}{f(x, I_1, I_2)} dx = \int \frac{\dot{u}}{u} \frac{1}{\dot{u}} du = \int \frac{1}{u} du = \ln|u| + C$$

back to the $f(x, I_1, I_2)$, we get:

$$\int \frac{\dot{f}(x, I_1, I_2)}{f(x, I_1, I_2)} dx = \ln|f(x, I_1, I_2)| + C$$

Example 2

$$1) \int \frac{(1 - 2I_1 + 3I_2)x^3}{(3 - 6I_1 + 9I_2)x^4 + 4I_1 + I_2} dx = \frac{1}{3} \ln|(3 - 6I_1 + 9I_2)x^4 + 4I_1 + I_2| + C$$

$$2) \int \frac{(4 - I_1 + I_2)e^{(4-I_1+I_2)x+5}}{e^{(4-I_1+I_2)x+5} - 10I_2} dx = \ln|e^{(4-I_1+I_2)x+5} - 10I_2| + C$$

$$3) \int \tan((1 + I_1 + I_2)x + 7I_1) dx = \int \frac{\sin((1 + I_1 + I_2)x + 7I_1)}{\cos((1 + I_1 + I_2)x + 7I_1)} dx$$

$$= -\left(1 + \left[\frac{-1}{(1)(2)(3)}\right] I_1 - \left[\frac{1}{(1)(2)}\right] I_2\right) \ln|\cos((1 + I_1 + I_2)x + 7I_1)| + C$$

$$= \left(-1 + \frac{1}{6}I_1 + \frac{1}{2}I_2\right) \ln|\cos((1 + I_1 + I_2)x + 7I_1)| + C$$

$$4) \int \frac{1}{1 + \tan(5 - 2I_1 - 2I_2)x} dx = \int \frac{1}{1 + \frac{\sin(5 - 2I_1 - 2I_2)x}{\cos(5 - 2I_1 - 2I_2)x}} dx$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \int \frac{2 \cos(5 - 2I_1 - 2I_2)x}{\cos(5 - 2I_1 - 2I_2)x + \sin(5 - 2I_1 - 2I_2)x} dx$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \int \frac{\cos(5 - 2I_1 - 2I_2)x + \sin(5 - 2I_1 - 2I_2)x + \cos(5 - 2I_1 - 2I_2)x - \sin(5 - 2I_1 - 2I_2)x}{\cos(5 - 2I_1 - 2I_2)x + \sin(5 - 2I_1 - 2I_2)x} dx$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \int dx + \frac{1}{2} \int \frac{\cos(5 - 2I_1 - 2I_2)x - \sin(5 - 2I_1 - 2I_2)x}{\cos(5 - 2I_1 - 2I_2)x + \sin(5 - 2I_1 - 2I_2)x} dx$$

$$= \frac{1}{2}x + \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{1}{5} + \left[\frac{10}{(5)(3)(1)}\right] I_1 - \left[\frac{-2}{(5)(3)}\right] I_2\right) \ln|\cos(5 - 2I_1 - 2I_2)x + \sin(5 - 2I_1 - 2I_2)x| + C$$

$$= \frac{1}{2}x + \left(\frac{1}{10} + \frac{1}{3}I_1 + \frac{1}{15}I_2\right) \ln|\cos(5 - 2I_1 - 2I_2)x + \sin(5 - 2I_1 - 2I_2)x| + C$$

Theorem 3

Let $f: R(I_1, I_2) \rightarrow R(I_1, I_2)$, then:

$$\int \frac{\dot{f}(x, I_1, I_2)}{\sqrt{f(x, I_1, I_2)}} dx = 2\sqrt{f(x, I_1, I_2)} + C$$

Proof:

put: $f(x, I_1, I_2) = u \quad \Rightarrow \dot{f}(x, I_1, I_2) dx = du$

$$\Rightarrow dx = \frac{1}{\dot{f}(x, I_1, I_2)} du$$

$$\Rightarrow dx = \frac{1}{\dot{u}} du$$

$$\int \frac{\dot{f}(x, I_1, I_2)}{\sqrt{f(x, I_1, I_2)}} dx = \int \frac{\dot{u}}{\sqrt{u}} \frac{1}{\dot{u}} du = \int \frac{1}{\sqrt{u}} du = 2\sqrt{u} + C$$

back to $f(x, I_1, I_2)$, we get:

$$\int \frac{\dot{f}(x, I_1, I_2)}{\sqrt{f(x, I_1, I_2)}} dx = 2\sqrt{f(x, I_1, I_2)} + C$$

Example 3

$$1) \int \frac{-(1 + 2I_1 + 2I_2)x + 5I_2}{\sqrt{(2 + 4I_1 + 4I_2)x^2 - 10I_2x}} dx = -\sqrt{(2 + 4I_1 + 4I_2)x^2 - 10I_2x} + C$$

$$2) \int \frac{(5 - 3I_1 + 8I_2)x^2}{\sqrt{(5 - 3I_1 + 8I_2)x^3 - 2I_1 + 7I_2}} dx = \frac{2}{3}\sqrt{(5 - 3I_1 + 8I_2)x^3 - 2I_1 + 7I_2} + C$$

Theorem 4

$f: R(I_1, I_2) \rightarrow R(I_1, I_2)$, then:

$$\int [f(x, I_1, I_2)]^n \dot{f}(x, I_1, I_2) dx = \frac{[f(x, I_1, I_2)]^{n+1}}{n+1} + C$$

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{put: } f(x, I_1, I_2) = u & \Rightarrow \dot{f}(x, I_1, I_2) dx = du \\ & \Rightarrow dx = \frac{1}{\dot{f}(x, I_1, I_2)} du \\ & \Rightarrow dx = \frac{1}{\dot{u}} du \end{aligned}$$

$$\int [f(x, I_1, I_2)]^n \dot{f}(x, I_1, I_2) dx = \int u^n \dot{u} \frac{1}{\dot{u}} du = \int u^n du = \frac{u^{n+1}}{n+1} + C$$

back to $f(x, I_1, I_2)$, we get:

$$\int [f(x, I_1, I_2)]^n \dot{f}(x, I_1, I_2) dx = \frac{[f(x, I_1, I_2)]^{n+1}}{n+1} + C$$

Example 5

$$\begin{aligned} 1) \int x^2 [(3 + 2I_1 + 2I_2)x^3]^{12} dx &= \frac{1}{3} \int 3x^2 [(3 + 2I_1 + 2I_2)x^3]^{12} dx \\ &= \frac{1}{9 + 6I_1 + 6I_2} \frac{[(3 + 2I_1 + 2I_2)x^3]^{13}}{13} + C \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{9} + \left[\frac{-54}{(9)(15)(21)} \right] I_1 - \left[\frac{6}{(9)(15)} \right] I_2 \right) \frac{[(3 + 2I_1 + 2I_2)x^3]^{13}}{13} + C \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{9} - \frac{2}{105} I_1 - \frac{2}{45} I_2 \right) \frac{[(3 + 2I_1 + 2I_2)x^3]^{13}}{13} + C \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2) \int \frac{1}{\sqrt{(2 + I_1 + I_2)x - I_1 + 2I_2}} \left(\sqrt{(2 + I_1 + I_2)x - I_1 + 2I_2} \right)^{14} dx \\ = 2 \left(\frac{1}{2} - \left[\frac{1}{(3)(4)} \right] I_1 - \left[\frac{1}{(2)(3)} \right] I_2 \right) \frac{\left(\sqrt{(2 + I_1 + I_2)x - I_1 + 2I_2} \right)^{15}}{15} + C \end{aligned}$$

$$= \left(1 - \frac{1}{6}I_1 - \frac{1}{3}I_2\right) \frac{\left(\sqrt{(2 + I_1 + I_2)x - I_1 + 2I_2}\right)^{15}}{15} + C$$

3. Conclusions

The integral is very important in our life, and is used especially for example in calculating areas whose shape is not familiar. This led us to study the refined neutrosophic indefinite integral that contain two parts of indeterminacy (I_1, I_2) . Where the method of integration by substitution are applied to the neutrosophic functions by presenting several theorems through which we were able to apply them to directly find the refined neutrosophic indefinite integral.

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